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Taxonomic observations on *Monorthochaeta* (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae) in Ukraine, and biological notes on *M. nigra*

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Gumovsky, A. V. & Fursov, V. N. Taxonomic observations on *Monorthochaeta* (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae) in Ukraine, and biological notes on *M. nigra*. — Two species of egg parasitoids of the trichogrammatine genus *Monorthochaeta* Blood, 1923 are recorded in Ukraine: *M. nigra* Blood and *M. galatica* Nowicki. *Monorthochaeta adanaensis* Doğanlar, 2002 **syn. n.** is considered a junior synonym of *M. nigra* Blood, 1923. The ovipositing behavior, egg and larva of *M. nigra*, a parasitoid of eggs of tortoise beetles (Cassidinae), were studied. Despite differences in habitus on intervals after oviposition, only one larval instar with variable body shape and length is reported for *M. nigra*.

Key words: Chalcidoidea, egg parasitoids, behavior, immature morphology, Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Asteraceae.

Гумовський, О. В. і Фурсов, В. М. Таксономічні спостереження з *Monorthochaeta* (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae) в Україні та біологічні нотатки щодо *M. nigra*. — В Україні зареєстровано два види яйцевих паразитоїдів-трихограматид роду *Monorthochaeta* Blood, 1923: *M. nigra* Blood та *M. galatica* Nowicki. *Monorthochaeta adanaensis* Doğanlar, 2002 **syn. n.** визнано молодшим синонімом *M. nigra* Blood, 1923. Вивчено поведінку при відкладанні яєць, морфологію яйця та личинки *M. nigra*, яйцевого паразитоїда жуків-щитоносок (Cassidinae). Незважаючи на відмінності в габітусі, у *M. nigra* знайдено лише одну личинкову вікову стадію, яка характеризується мінливою формою та довжиною тіла.

Ключові слова: Chalcidoidea, яйцеві паразитоїди, поведінка, морфологія преімагінальних фаз, Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Asteraceae.

Introduction

The family Trichogrammatidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) encompasses mostly egg parasitoids. Currently the family includes about 800 species and 95 genera (Noyes, 2022). Most trichogrammatids with known biology develop as egg parasitoids in hosts of 12 insect orders (Fursov, 2015). Many trichogrammatid species are of economic importance, chiefly through their value as biocontrol agents. However, biology and immature morphology of many species remain unknown.

The current classification of Trichogrammatidae was proposed by Viggiani (1971, 1984) and is based mostly on the structures of male genitalia. Two subfamilies are recognized: Trichogrammatinae (with the tribes Trichogrammatini and Paracentrobiini) and Oligositinae (with the tribes Oligositini and Chaetostichini). The male genitalia of most Oligositinae are reduced and modified to form a

sole tubular structure which lacks volcellae, parameres and a discernible aedeagus. The species of the tribe Oligositini have the extremely reduced male genitalia. However, the species of Chaetostichini have the male genitalia with open and developed anterodorsal aperture, parameres and separate aedeagus. The Palaearctic genus *Monorthochaeta* Blood comprises two European species: *M. nigra* Blood and *M. galatica* Nowicki (Fursov, 2015). Another species, *M. adanaensis*, was described by Doğanlar (2002) from Türkiye (Adana region). Also, one species, *M. platensis* De Santis (1957), was described from Argentina in the genus *Ufens* Girault, and later was considered as *Monorthochaeta* by Doutt & Viggiani (1968). Then this species was transferred to the genus *Zagella* Girault by Triapitsyn (2003), and finally considered as *Burksiella* De Santis by Pinto (2006) and Ávila-Rodríguez et al. (2011).

The species of *Monorthochaeta* were recorded as egg parasitoids of tortoise beetles of the genus *Cassida*

(Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Cassidinae) (Noyes, 2022). Some experiments were carried out to study the longevity, parasitism rate and success of *M. nigra* parasitizing the tortoise beetle *C. vittata* in Egypt (Awadalla, 1993, 1996). However, the details of morphology and development of immature stages have not yet been studied. So, this paper is focused on shedding light on the diversity and biological traits of *Monorthochaeta* in Ukraine, as well as on some taxonomic notes on its species.

Material and methods

The eggs of a tortoise beetle were collected on thistle plants (Figs 1a, b) at a roadside near Hlobyne (Staryi Khutir village, 49.4421120, 33.2032327) in Kremenchuk Raion of Poltava Oblast in June 2021. The egg parasitoids (*M. nigra*) were reared in late June 2021. The laboratory culture of tortoise beetle *Cassida rubiginosa* (Figs 1c–e) was also started in late June 2021, in the laboratory of the Institute of Organic Agriculture (Arnika Agroindustrial Group, Hlobyne, Ukraine). Freshly laid eggs of beetles became available in late June and July. The freshly laid host eggs were proposed to the parasitoid females for oviposition. The parasitized eggs were dissected immediately after oviposition and within each 7–10 hours afterwards to trace immature development of the parasitoid. The limited number and life span of the parasitoids allowed tracing their development only on the egg and larval stage.

The materials studied are deposited in the collection of the I.I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, NAS Ukraine (Kyiv, Ukraine) — SIZK. The type materials of *M. adanaensis* Doğanlar, 2002 (Fig. 3e) were submitted as a loan by Prof. M. Doğanlar, the Entomology Museum of Mus-

tafa Kemal University, Agriculture Faculty, Department of Plant Protection, Antakya (Hatay, Türkiye) — MKU.

“Türkiye” is preferred to “Turkey” in referring to the country Republic of Türkiye, according to UN recommendations.

Most photos were made with the camera Canon PowerShot A650 IS connected to Optika compound microscope, but also with the Olympus digital camera C-4040ZOOM connected to the Olympus system microscope CX-41, under Olympus DP-Soft programme (Version 3.2).

Results

Family Trichogrammatidae

Subfamily Oligositinae

Tribe Chaetostichini

Genus *Monorthochaeta* Blood, 1923

Monorthochaeta Blood, 1923.

Monorthochaeta Blood & Kryger, 1928.

Diagnosis. Body black, shining. Antenna with 2 anelli, 2 strongly joined funiculars, clava 3-segmented, elongate, sharpened apically in female, short, oval, 2- or 3-segmented in male. Fore wing of female with wide blade bearing dense, irregular setation, marginal fringe about 0.1× of maximum wing width, marginal vein as long as submarginal vein or shorter, stigmal vein long, with constricted neck and rounded stigma. Male alate or apterous; if alate, the wing with scarce setation on disk and with marginal fringe longer than in female.

Distribution. Only 2 species are recorded in the world, both in Palearctic region (Doutt & Viggiani, 1968).

Key to Palearctic species

- 1 Fore wing 2.5 times as long as broad (Figs 3d, 5d). Hind basitarsus about 2.0 times longer than 2nd tarsomere (Fig. 4d). Antennal clava of male two-segmented (Fig. 2d). Apodemes of aedeagus long, attached to the base of phallobase (Fig. 2g)..... *M. nigra* Blood
- Fore wing 1.9–2.2 times as long as broad (Fig. 5e). Hind basitarsus about 1.0–1.2 times longer than 2nd tarsomere (Fig. 4D). Antennal clava of male three-segmented (Fig. 5c). Apodemes of aedeagus short, attached nearly to the middle of phallobase (Fig. 4e). *M. galatica* Nowicki

Monorthochaeta nigra Blood, 1923 (Figs 2, 3, 5a, d, 6–8)

Monorthochaeta nigra Blood, 1923: 257.

Monorthochaeta adanaensis Doğanlar, 2006: 251, **syn. n.**

Type material studied (Fig. 3E). Holotype ♀ *M. adanaensis* (Figs 3a–d), “Türkiye, Adana, Balcali, August 1999, ex eggs *Cassida* (coll. M. D. Ghawami)”, on glass slide №1888. Paratypes: 2♀, same label, ex eggs *Cassida rubiginosa* on *Cynara scolymus*; 2♂, same label (separate glass slides №1889, №1892), marked “allotype, paratype” (on separate glass slides №1890, №1891) (Fig. 2e–g) (MKU).

Other material studied. Ukraine: Cherkasy Oblast, Uman Raion, Zhytnyky, “Kuibyshev” collective farm, 7–8.06.1984, ex eggs *Cassida*

nebulosa, emerged 20.06.1984, 2♀, 1♂ (Yu.P. Bichuk) [♀ antenna and wing – slides 107, 108]; Poltava Oblast, Kremenchuk Raion, nr. Hlobyne, “Staryi Khutir”, reared from egg set of tortoise beetle on thistle leaf, coll. 21.06.2021, reared end of 06.2021, 2♀ (used for biological experiments) (Fig. 2a–c), 1♂ (Fig. 2d), (A. Gumovsky); Kherson Oblast, 10.08.1985, ex eggs of tortoise beetle, 2♀ (V. Fursov); Crimea, near Nikita village, swept from Gramineae and Fabaceae on grassy hills in forest 18.05.1994, 1♀ (V. Fursov); Türkiye: Isparta, 8.05.2002, 1♀ (M.D. Ghawami); Kırşehir Province, forest, 19.05.2005, 1♀ (on glass slide №1894) (M.D. Ghawami); Hatay, Reyhanlı district, Tell Tayinat, 05.05.2005, 2♀ (on glass slides 1893, 1896) (M. Doğanlar) (SIZK).

Fig. 1: a — thistle plants on a roadside in the vicinities of Staryi Khutir (Ukraine, Poltava Oblast, near Hlobyne), leaf with egg set of tortoise beetle on underside (red framed); b — egg set, from where the adults of *Monorthochaeta nigra* Blood were reared, and which is framed in a; c, d — adults (color variations) of the host beetle, *Cassida rubiginosa*, on thistle leaf; e — young thistle shoots planted in pots for maintenance of tortoise beetle laboratory culture and biological experiments on *M. nigra* (the Institute of Organic Agriculture, Arnika Agroindustrial Group, Hlobyne, Ukraine).

Fig. 2. *Monorthochaeta nigra* Blood, adult: a–c — female (Ukraine, Poltava Oblast), d — male (Ukraine, Poltava Oblast); f–g — male paratype of *M. adanaensis* Doğanlar; e, f — legs; g — genitalia.

Fig. 3. a-d — *Monorthochaeta nigra* (female holotype of *M. adanaensis* Doğanlar). a, b — antenna; c — legs; d — fore wing; e — studied type series of *M. adanaensis*.

Host. Tortoise beetles, in particular *Cassida* spp. (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae, Cassidini) (Noyes, 2022).

Distribution. England (Blood, 1923; Blood & Kryger, 1928), France, Italy (Nowicki, 1940), Hungary, Czech Republic (Noyes, 2022), Ukraine (Fursov, 2015), Türkiye (Doğanlar, 2002), Egypt (Awadalla, 1993, 1996; Hendawy & El-Fakharany, 2017).

Discussion. Synonymy of *M. adanaensis* Doğanlar with *M. nigra* Blood is proposed here as resultant from the comparison of the type specimens of *M. adanaensis* with reared material of *M. nigra* and its original description. Doğanlar (2002) stated that *M. adanaensis* differs from *M. nigra* in having the antennal clava of both sexes with a long terminal spine and the clava of male being twice as long as broad, and the second clavomere of male being twice as long as the first clavomere (whereas there is no terminal spine in female, the male clava is just slightly longer than broad, and its second clavomere is just slightly longer than the first clavomere in *M. nigra*). However, the discussed characters vary in *M. nigra*. They are also not very distinct in the type specimens, so we consider them intraspecific variations. Instead, the presence of the characters listed in the key, the long hind basitarsus in particular, suggest that *M. nigra* Blood, 1923 and *M. adanaensis* Doğanlar, 2002 concern one and the same species, so the synonymy of the names is proposed.

Monorthochaeta galatica Nowicki, 1940 (Figs 4a-c, e, f, 5b, c, e)

Monorthochaeta galatica Nowicki, 1940: 631.

Monorthochaeta galatica obscuripes Nowicki, 1940: 632; syn. by Doult, Viggiani, 1968: 523.

Material. Ukraine: Vinnytsia Oblast, Yampilskiy Raion, village Oksanivka (Fleminda), bank of Dniester river, swept from grass, 20.07.1988, 3♂ (V. Fursov); Cherkasy Oblast, Uman Raion, Zhytnyky, 'Kuibyshev' collective farm, 7-8.06.1984, ex eggs *Cassida nebulosa*, emerged 20.06.1984, 2♀ (Figs 4a-c), 1♂ (Yu.P. Bichuk) [♀ antenna and wing – slides 303, 313, 314, ♂ antenna and wing – slide 302]; Kyiv Oblast, 05.07.1986, ex eggs tortoise beetle, 2♀ (V. Fursov); Kherson Oblast, The Black Sea Biosphere Reserve, Potievskiy plot, ex single egg of *Cassida* sp., 01.06.1985, emerged 18.06.1985, 1♂ (V. Fursov); Armenia: village Dzithankov, on a leaf of *Polygonum* sp., 09.07.1951, 1♀ (D. Hachatryan), slide 833; Türkiye: Nurdağı, Adac. Sul, 370980 N, 364733 E, coll.05.07.2007, 1♀ (M. Doğanlar); Russian Federation: Western Siberia, Tomsk District, Pozdnevo, 14.07.1985, ex eggs of tortoise beetle, emerged 5.07.1985, 1♂ (Figs 4e, f) (G.F. Vecher), on slide 511 (SIZK).

Host. Tortoise beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae, Cassidini) (Noyes, 2022).

Distribution. Hungary, Poland (Nowicki, 1935), Ukraine (Fursov, 2015), Türkiye (Doğanlar, 2002), Russian Federation (Western Siberia), Armenia (new records).

Behavioral observations and immature development of *Monorthochaeta nigra*

The life cycle of *M. nigra* is correlated with the life cycle of its host, the tortoise beetle *Cassida rubiginosa*. The adults of *M. nigra* were reared from freshly laid host eggs in late June in Poltava Oblast of Ukraine. So,

it is highly likely that the first females (overwintered or emerged from overwintered host eggs) appear in the end of May, when thistle host plants are grown and the host beetles start their oviposition (Figs 1a-d). The adults of *M. nigra* stay alive for about a week, when fed with honey-water mixture. If the egg parasitism is successful, the next generation of parasitoids may appear about three weeks later, what coincides with the ending of oviposition time of the host beetles (end of July). The parasitoids developing in the host eggs laid in July, are likely to overwinter: either as immature (larva or pupa), or as hatched adults.

Oviposition

The mated females are attracted by the host eggs: either uncovered (Fig. 6a), or covered by the host's faeces (Fig. 6b) as it is common for tortoise beetles (Fig. 1B). Once the female locates the egg, it stops walking, drums the egg surface with antennae (Fig. 6d) and eventually bends its gaster and hooks the ovipositor saw in the egg chorion (Fig. 6c). Then it pushes the gaster down, punctures the chorion and starts twisting the gaster. The drilling of the host egg lasts for about 30 sec, and ends up with either host feeding or egg deposition.

Immature stages

Egg. The freshly laid egg is elongate and spindle-shaped (stalked), with micropile situated on a longer anterior stalk (Figs 6e, f). It is about 0.2 mm long, 0.05 mm wide. The yolk is discernible as a mass enclosed in an internal membrane. An intensive proliferation of cells starts nearly immediately after oviposition.

Larva. Only one instar was detected in *M. nigra* despite the larvae of different length and body shape were isolated from the parasitized host eggs. Also, no molts were recorded during larval development, so we assume this to be one continuous stage. The larva has three habitual forms (vermiform, pyriform and sacciform) similar to the ones described by Flanders (1937).

The larva hatches about 36 hours after oviposition; it is of subrectangular shape (vermiform), about 0.3 mm long, about 0.12 mm wide then (Fig. 7a). The larva is apneustic, non-segmented, and characterized by the long sickle-shaped mandibles, which are about 0.05 mm long, and the large hind gut. The larva is getting longer about 48 hours later, about 0.4 mm long, 0.15 mm wide, with hind gut filled with granules (Fig. 7b). There is also no obvious segmentation and the mandibles are the same (Figs 7d, e).

The larva turns pyriform about 60 hours later (Fig. 7f). Its posterior part is bulged and filled with dark contents. The anterior part is narrowed, it is bearing a distinct head capsule (cranium) with the long sharp sickle-shaped mandibles being 0.05 mm long. Three weak swellings are observable in the area between the cranium and the bulged part; this part remains flexible and can retract and protract (Fig. 7g, h). This may suggest a vestigial segmentation of a thoracic part of the larva's body.

Fig. 4. a–c — *Monorthochaeta galatica* Nowicki (Ukraine, Cherkasy Oblast, Uman Raion); d — *M. nigra* and *M. galatica*, hind tarsi (tr1–3 — tarsomeres); e, f — *M. galatica* (Russian Federation, Tomsk District, slide 511): e — male genitalia; f — mid leg.

The larva is notably larger, sacciform, when about 70 hours pass since the oviposition and segmentation is still traceable in the thoracic area (Fig. 8d). The larva still has same sickle-shaped mandibles being 0.05 mm long (Fig. 8d).

It has vestigial tracheal system, but still apneustic (Fig. 8c). And after 90 hours since the oviposition the larva has nearly finished the destructive host feeding and occupies the entire volume of the host egg (Fig. 8b).

Fig. 5. *Monorthochaeta nigra* (a, d) and *M. galatica* Nowicki (b, c, e): a — female antenna, a–c — antenna (a, b — female, c — male), d, e — fore wing.

Fig. 6. *Monorthochaeta nigra* Blood: a-d — female ovipositing (scale bare is as in A); e, f — freshly laid egg.

Fig. 7. *Monorthochaeta nigra* Blood, larva: a — about 36 hours after oviposition; b, c — about 48 hours after oviposition; d — head of the larva shown in b, enlarged (mandible arrowed); e — enlarged head of the larva shown in c; f–h — about 60 hours after oviposition.

Fig. 8. *Monorthochaeta nigra* Blood: a — parasitized egg, about 100 hours after oviposition; b — replete larva within host egg (pulsing mid gut), about 90 hours after oviposition; c, d — replete larva, about 72 hours after oviposition: c — final instar, habitus; d — body in lateral view (head in dorsal view in inset).

Discussion

Our studies have confirmed that *Monorthochaeta* includes only two species: *M. nigra* and *M. galatica*, which are recored in Ukraine and widely distributed across Palearctics. Both species are of economic importance, since they are associated with tortoise beetles, which may act as pests or biocontrol agents of weeds.

The biology of *M. nigra* demonstrates the phenomenon of the presence of only one instar. This phenomenon is reported for some other trichogrammatids, the species of *Trichogramma*, in particular (Jarjees & Merritt, 2002; Woelke *et al.*, 2019). The existence of only one instar is supported by the possession of the mandibles of the same shape and length, and also by the lack of any signs of molts in the larva of *M. nigra*. Likewise, in the *Trichogramma* species (Jarjees & Merritt, 2002; Woelke *et al.*, 2019), the teguments of *M. nigra* are soft and distensible, so the body shape of the larva changes along with larva's feeding (Figs 7, 8). It is remarkable, that there are no sutures which may suggest segmentation of the larva. However, the subdivision of the anterior part of the larva's body into three swelled sections in the larvae at about 48–72 hours after oviposition (Figs 7f–h, 8c, d), suggest at least vestigial segmentation of the thoracic part of the larva.

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